

DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT, PLASMA WIND TUNNEL AND FLIGHT TEST OF A FLEXIBLE THERMAL PROTECTION SYSTEM FOR THE ICARUS INFLATABLE HEAT SHIELD

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ABSTRACT

The EU-funded ICARUS project (HORIZON EUROPE, Grant No. 101134997) aims to advance key technologies for reusable space transportation systems, focusing on Inflatable Heat Shields (IHS) for launch vehicle stage recovery. The project targets TRL6 by maturing critical components such as the Flexible Thermal Protection System (FTPS), inflatable structures, and health monitoring sensors. Activities include mission/system design, flight testing of an IHS demonstrator on a sounding rocket, Plasma Wind Tunnel tests simulating orbital re-entry, and post-test analyses for model validation. This paper presents the development of the FTPS for the ICARUS Aerodemonstrator, covering requirement definition, material selection, sample testing, and breadboard evaluations. It also details the design and planning of representative SCIROCCO wind tunnel tests, the FTPS layout, current design status, numerical thermal modeling and results, and preliminary experimental findings. Future work to support FTPS qualification, manufacturing, and integration on the re-entry vehicle is also outlined.

Index Terms— Flexible Thermal Protection System (FTPS), Numerical Thermal Model, High-Temperature Testing, Orbital Re-entry, PWT, TGA

1. INTRODUCTION

ICARUS stands for “Inflatable Concept Aero-shell for the Recovery of a re-Usable launcher Stage”, and it targets maturing up to TRL-6 the technologies enabling Inflatable Heat Shields for Earth re-entry missions.

In its baseline, an Aerodemonstrator of an IHS will be flight-tested through a sub-orbital flight executed by a sounding rocket launched in ESRANGE and managed by DLR-MORABA.

A concept of the ICARUS re-entry vehicle is given in Fig. 1. In Europe, the two projects EFESTO and EFESTO-2, funded by the European Commission respectively under the programs H2020 (2019-2022) and under Horizon Europe

(2022-2024), constitute the solid playground that ICARUS is leaning on, [1][2][3][4].

Fig. 1. ICARUS Re-entry concept.

The aforementioned projects can be considered, respectively, the grandfather and the father of ICARUS, because they allowed to bloom and grow-up in the EU the knowledge and capabilities in the field of IHSs.

However, although a significant TRL increase was achieved in the frame of EFESTO and EFESTO-2, both were focused on ground-verification only.

Instead, the ICARUS project is a flight demonstration initiative aiming at bringing together the results obtained so far, with in addition a significant delta-development together with validation of the technologies and system capabilities in a flight-relevant environment.

In that perspective, the project will pursue the following end goals:

- a. complete the maturation on ground of the key technologies as Flexible Thermal Protection Systems, Inflatable Structure and Health Monitoring Sensors;
- b. carry out a mission/system design loop to realize a meaningful-scale demonstrator of a re-entry vehicle based on an Inflatable Heat Shield;
- c. execute the flight mission and the post-flight analysis for technology performance evaluation, system

behaviour identification, and models verification/cross-correlation;

The project organization (Fig. 2) consists of eleven partners under coordination of Indra-Deimos, for a full EU team, and it brings together key players with a relevant heritage in the field of sounding rockets and flight testing, as well as in engineering and technology development of re-entry systems and Inflatable Heat Shield systems.

Fig. 2. ICARUS Industrial Team.

The role of CIRA is leading the development of the Flexible Thermal Protection System through numerical modelling and Plasma Wind Tunnel (PWT) experimental testing.

2. F-TPS DESIGN

The Thermal Protection System (TPS) constitutes the outermost layer of the aeroshell and acts as an external shield designed to safeguard the inflatable structure, as well as all internal components beneath it, including the structural tube and the onboard avionics. The TPS primarily interfaces with the Inflatable Structure and the Cold Structure of the re-entry vehicle, with a specific mechanical connection foreseen at the Nose Tip. The high-level requirement for the design of the F-TPS is defined based on the re-entry trajectory shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. ICARUS sub-orbital flight trajectory

Starting from this preliminary trajectory, a detailed CFD analysis was subsequently carried out to refine the thermal and mechanical environment and provide more accurate input for the sizing and validation of the F-TPS, that, given its direct exposure to the incident aerodynamic flow (shown in Fig. 4), shall have adequate mechanical strength and high emissivity to enhance radiative cooling.

Fig. 4 ICARUS expected aerodynamic flow.

The complication of a flexible heat shield is the folding of the inflatable structure. This means that the TPS must be composed of materials that have an optimal balance between flexibility and thermal efficiency, and it must feature a very small thickness because of the strict volume allowed for the packing. For this reason, the baseline solution of the TPS chosen for the suborbital flight test is a multi-layer configuration composed of two categories of materials: external protection and insulating layers. The latter shall present low thermal conductivity to delay the propagation of the thermal wave and to ensure that the inflatable structure remains within its maximum allowable operating temperature. Due to their inherently low density, insulating materials typically exhibit limited mechanical strength and may degrade when directly exposed to high-temperature air flow. For this reason, external protection shall not only resist elevated temperature but also have low permeability. Based on their thermal and structural performance, the material selection focused on Nextel ceramic fabrics for the

external protection, due to their high-temperature resistance, low permeability, and foldability, and on Sigratherm felts for the insulation layer, given their excellent thermal insulation capabilities up to 1500 °C, both shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Nextel (left) and Sigratherm (right) fabrics

3. F-TPS THERMAL SIZING

A preliminary sizing of the TPS was performed using a 1D parametric approach in which, for each trajectory, multiple analyses were performed changing the thickness of each insulation layer until the maximum temperature reached on the IS along the trajectory was lower than a predefined parameter. In particular, a TPS made of 2 layers, Nextel and Sigratherm, was considered, as shown in Fig. 6. The IS in these preliminary analyses was not taken into account.

Fig. 6 TPS 1D Numerical Model.

The main driving parameter is the maximum temperature sustainable during the re-entry by these materials, which is around 1600°C for Nextel and 350°C for IS.

The boundary conditions applied to the analyses were the following:

- The history of heat flux along the trajectory, applied on the outer side of the F-TPS (Nextel)
- Radiation from Nextel towards the surrounding environment (at 22°C) with $\epsilon=0.8$
- Radiation from Sigratherm towards inner inflated volume at 100°C with $\epsilon=0.8$

In particular, the history of heat flux for these analyses was extrapolated from the trajectories elaborated by DEIMOS and Fig. 7 shows the history of heat flux along the most demanding of these trajectories, which is the one that considers a re-entry mass of 350kg [5]. In terms of thicknesses, four cases were analysed with 3, 6, 12 and 18mm of Sigratherm.

The results of this analysis are shown in Table 1. A TPS made of 0.5mm of Nextel and 3mm of Sigratherm seems to be suitable.

350KG	
CASE	Temperature on lower face of Sigratherm [°C]
3.5MM	352
6.5MM	253
12.5MM	157
18.5MM	124

Table 1. 1D parametric analysis results.

These results were used to perform a very preliminary estimation of the total mass of the F-TPS. In particular, the total volume of the F-TPS was estimated using the CAD surface of the structure (neglecting Nose and backside, as shown in Fig. 8) and multiplying it by the thickness of the two layers. Hence, the total mass was evaluated considering the density of each material and applying a 20% margin, that resulted in a total margined mass of about 15kg.

Fig. 7 Sub-orbital trajectory (350kg at re-entry).

Fig. 8. F-TPS external surface (no Nose).

In the mono-dimensional thermal model, an additional parametric study was carried on concerning the variation of material emissivity in order to evaluate its effects on the cold structure maximum temperature. The results are shown in Table 2 and what comes out is that obviously the temperature changes but not drastically, as expected.

350KG	
CASE	Temperature on lower face of Sigratherm [°C]
E 0,8	351
E 0,75	356
E 0,7	361

Table 2 Results of the analysis for different emissivity.

3.1 2D F-TPS analyses

More detailed sizing of the TPS was performed considering an axisymmetric 2D CFD analysis, performed on the geometry shown in Fig. 9, as input [6]. In this case the thickness of the TPS was fixed at the value obtained through the mono-dimensional analyses, which is 0.5mm for Nextel and 3mm for Sigratherm. From the 2D CFD performed by ONERA a distribution of convective heat transfer coefficient (H_c) was extracted along the body (Fig. 10). This distribution was then normalized by dividing all the values by the maximum of the distribution. In particular, the distribution related to the case of Mach 5.14 (maximum heat flux). The variation of H_c distribution along the trajectory was imposed by multiplying at each timestep this distribution by the value of H_c coming from trajectory analysis at the stagnation point (Fig. 11). The total temperature (T^0) was also taken from the trajectory (Fig. 12).

Fig. 9. 2D F-TPS Geometry.

For the 2D axisymmetric analysis the following BCs were considered:

- The normalized distribution of convective heat transfer coefficient, applied on the outer side of the F-TPS (Nextel)
- The history of H_c and T^0 along the trajectory (taken from 350kg trajectory)
- Radiation from Nextel towards the surrounding environment (at 22°C) with $\epsilon=0.8$

- Radiation from Sigratherm towards inner inflated cavity is modeled with $\epsilon=0.8$

At each timestep the normalized distribution of H_c is multiplied by the history of H_c extracted from the trajectory. In this way the convective heat transfer distribution at each timestep changes following the transient happening along the trajectory and at the stagnation point is always equal to the one shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 10. Convective heat transfer coefficient on the body.

Fig. 11 Convective heat transfer coefficient along the trajectory.

Fig. 12 Total temperature along the trajectory.

Fig. 13 shows the temperature distribution on the lower face of the Sigratherm layer at one timestep, in particular the one in which the Temperature at the stagnation point is maximum and equal to the one foreseen in the 1D analysis.

Fig. 13. T distribution on IS.

The temperature limit of 350°C is only exceeded in a very small region close to the stagnation point. This is not relevant because the nose will not be inflatable, and will be rigid, massive and will have much higher heat capacity and this will lead to much lower temperatures.

3.2 LEO re-entry F-TPS sizing

An additional F-TPS sizing was performed considering a re-entry from a Low Earth Orbit (LEO). This was deemed necessary because the objective of the project is to reach a TRL of 6 also for the FTPS, and since the suborbital flight aerothermal load will not allow such verification, it was necessary to obtain such a load form a potential LEO re-entry flight, in such a way to perform then a ground test in the

Plasma wind tunnel. In that perspective, a preliminary sizing of the TPS for orbital re-entry was performed using the same approach adopted for sub-orbital flight conditions.

The main driving parameter is the maximum temperature sustainable during the re-entry by these materials, which is around 1600°C for Nextel and 350°C (TBC) for IS.

For each analysis the following BCs were considered:

- The history of heat flux along the trajectory, applied on the outer side of the F-TPS (Nextel)
- Radiation from Nextel towards the surrounding environment (at 22°C) with $\epsilon=0.8$
- Radiation from Sigratherm towards inner part of IS at 100°C with $\epsilon=0.8$

Three cases have been analyzed with three different entry conditions at the entry point, corresponding to three different flight path angles at Entry Interface Point (EIP) -0.5° -1.5° and -2.5° , as shown in Fig. 14.

Peak heat flux in the three cases analyzed are 372 kW/m², 408 kW/m² and 463 kW/m², respectively. The results of these analyses are shown in Table 3 and is clearly visible how a F-TPS of 18.5mm in thickness is necessary in this case where the heat fluxes are more demanding due to the higher energy, typical of an orbital re-entry.

Fig. 14. LEO re-entry trajectories for different FPA.

FPA @EIP = $-0,5^\circ$	
CASE	Temperature on lower face of Sigratherm [°C]
6,5mm	521
12,5mm	415
18,5mm	340
24,5mm	274
30,5mm	222
36,5mm	184
42,5mm	158

Table 3. FEM results at -0.5° FPA.

4. TGA CHARACTERIZATION

As part of the ground development effort, a TGA characterization has been carried out in order to investigate Sigratherm degradation in atmospheres characterized by a gas mixture of O₂ and N₂, where the oxygen concentrations range from 0% to 21%. This graphite soft felt has been characterized through a TGA/DSC test campaign. All tests have been performed at CIRA's facilities, using a specific machine called SDT, which combines the features of Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Thermogravimetric Analysis.

The percentages of oxygen are related to its partial pressure, which in operative conditions, is assumed to be around 2 kPa, i.e., 2% of O₂. The experiments have been conducted in O₂ concentrations of 0%, 7%, 7.5%, 10%, 11%, and 21%. Table 4 gives an overview of the 22 tests performed.

CASE	Type of test	N° of trials	Oxygen %	Ramp of temperature [°C/min]	Sample [mg]
1-3	Ramp	3	0; 7.5; 11	20	>2.0*
4-5	Ramp	2	7; 10	50	>2.0*
6	Ramp	1	21 (air)	50	1.44*
7-8	Ramp	2	0; 7	50	2.0
9-10	Step	2	7	80	1.4*; 2.0
11-16	Step	5	7	80	2.0
17-19	Ramp	3	21 (air)	80	2.0
20-22	Ramp	3	21 (air)	50	2.0

Table 4. Test campaign overview.

4.1 Results: ramp tests

The first set of tests is performed with a heating ramp of 20°C/min and 50°C/min and samples with irregular shapes (identified with *). This is an important remark and will be a crucial aspect for accurate results when testing the room conditions (i.e., 21% of O₂). The oxygen percentages tested here are 0%, 7.5%, and 11%, and the results are shown in Fig. 1.

The results show a good resistance of Sigratherm at low oxygen percentages, but the degradation increases rapidly for oxygen-rich atmospheres, starting above 7.5%.

The experimental results have been confirmed by the other two trials performed at 7% and 10% of O₂ with a more uniform and homogeneous sample of 2 mg. The data are reported in Fig. 15, showing the rate of material degradation in different oxygen concentrations.

Fig. 15. Material response in different oxygen concentrations.

4.2 Results: step tests

These further sets of tests have been performed to confirm mass loss at some relevant temperatures for oxygen concentrations of 7%. In this case, the heating was not linear, but maintained for 2 minutes at every step, as reported in Fig. 16. Results proved the previous data, confirming the acceptable weight loss percentage of Sigratherm at high temperatures, with a maximum material consumption in the range of 20%, at the end of the heating phase.

Fig. 16. Temperature profile.

Fig. 17. Step tests weight loss.

4.3 Results: ramp tests on room conditions

Room condition tests are needed for the next furnace test. As already mentioned, in this case, the sample's geometry assumes a crucial role in providing reliable results in air. Two kinds of heating ramps have been used to reach 1100°C as fast as possible: three at 50°C/min and three at 80°C/min. Sigratherm degrades very quickly compared to the previous tests, with a fast rate of 60%/min at its peak. The sample completely degraded before reaching the final temperature. This could be an issue and will need great care for the upcoming tests in analogous conditions. The experimental activities proved the good resistance of Sigratherm in low oxygen concentrations, which is enough to give a safety margin for the orbital and suborbital test conditions, but the degradation becomes very important in air, so it must be considered carefully for the furnace tests.

Fig. 18. Room conditions: weight loss and rate.

5. PWT TEST CAMPAIGN

The crucial part of the ground development will be the execution of a plasma test campaign with replication of the sizing heat flux condition based on the LEO re-entry simulation. Hence this section reports the design and modeling of high-enthalpy tests in the SCIROCCO plasma wind tunnel to qualify the Flexible Thermal Protection Systems (FTPS). Two complementary test campaigns are foreseen: one featuring a rigid-mounted FTPS skirt segmented into various material configurations, and the second using a finalized FTPS integrated on a representative inflatable structure. These tests are designed to assess thermal, structural, and material behavior in a flight-representative environment.

The test conditions are derived from an orbital 2.5° flight path angle trajectory and aim to replicate peak heat fluxes (620kW/m²), total heat loads, and stagnation pressures (38hPa). The model, inspired by re-entry configurations, features a 60 mm diameter body and 72 mm nose radius.

Fig. 19 Test article in the test chamber (Nozzle F configuration).

Several operating conditions have been identified and reported in Table 5, using three nozzle configurations—D, E, and F—with exit diameters of 1150 mm, 1350 mm, and 50 mm, respectively.

Fig. 20 Mach flow field around the model in the test chamber, for three different nozzle configurations.

All the identified operating points are capable of replicating the heat flux at the model's stagnation point; however, only a subset of these conditions—those listed in the second row of the table—can reproduce both the heat flux and the static pressure. These conditions are particularly demanding for the facility, especially in terms of total pressure level and required air mass flow rate. In fact, they exceed the operational capabilities of Nozzle F. While they appear theoretically achievable with Nozzles D and E, their feasibility still requires verification and validation by CIRA PWT test engineering, considering the limitations of the facility's operational envelope.

	D NOZZLE		E NOZZLE		F NOZZLE	
	H ⁰	P ⁰	H ⁰	P ⁰	H ⁰	P ⁰
q _s	11.09	3.53	11.85	3.18	15.25	6.30
q _s and p _s	9.09	7.10	9.04	8.98	NA	NA

Table 5 PWT test conditions.

Fig. 21 presents representative wall heat flux and surface temperature profiles on the model under the two operating conditions identified for the nozzle D configuration. The lower total pressure condition (red lines) is unable to replicate the target stagnation point static pressure, whereas the higher total pressure condition achieves a closer match. However, in terms of wall heat flux, both operating conditions demonstrate comparable accuracy in meeting the target distributions.

Fig. 21 Wall heat flux and wall pressure for Nozzle D test conditions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the development of the Flexible TPS for the ICARUS project. The design concept was introduced, followed by a discussion on the selection of materials for the F-TPS based on thermal, mechanical, and integration requirements. The sizing of the system was supported by 1D and 2D numerical analyses aimed at evaluating its thermal performance under representative operating conditions. Thermo-oxidative properties of the materials were investigated through TGA analyses.

Future activities will focus on high-temperature furnace testing of representative breadboards to assess the performance of the selected materials and stitching solutions under extreme thermal conditions, progressively moving toward a flight-representative configuration, that will be thermo-mechanically validated via Plasma Wind Tunnel (PWT) testing.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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More information at:

- <https://www.he-icarus-project.eu/>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134997>

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